

ENHANCEMENT OF THE EXTREME TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN

Zebiniso Khasanova¹, Nargiza Akhrorova²

¹Student of “Silk Road” International University of Tourism and Cultural Heritage, ²Senior Lecturer of “Silk Road” International University of Tourism and Cultural Heritage

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15605905>

Abstract. According to several sources, Uzbekistan is suitable place for extreme tourism due to the existence of applicable sites. However, this sphere of tourism has not adequately developed yet. This paper firstly explains the meaning of the extreme tourism and counts resulting benefits, such as economic growth and protection of natural spots. Secondly, the appropriate locations in Uzbekistan are founded from the literature. Finally, advice is given on opening new tour agencies specialize on adventure tour packages and which service include internet-based platform, with the promotion through it.

Keywords: Uzbekistan, extreme tourism, internet-based platform.

Annotatsiya. Turli manbalarga ko‘ra, O‘zbekiston ekstremal turizm uchun mos joy hisoblanadi, chunki bu yerda shunday turizm uchun qulay joylar mavjud. Biroq, ushbu turizm sohasi hali yetarlicha rivojlanmagan. Ushbu maqolada avvalo ekstremal turizm tushunchasi izohlanadi va u orqali erishiladigan foydalar, masalan, iqtisodiy o‘sish va tabiat go‘shalari muhofazasi ko‘rib chiqiladi. Keyinchalik, adabiyotlar asosida O‘zbekistondagi mos joylar aniqlanadi. Nihoyat, sarguzasht tur paketlariga ixtisoslashgan, internet platformasi orqali xizmat ko‘rsatadigan va reklama qiladigan yangi turistik agentliklar ochish bo‘yicha tavsiyalar beriladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: O‘zbekiston, ekstremal turizm, internet-platforma.

Аннотация. Согласно нескольким источникам, Узбекистан является подходящим местом для экстремального туризма благодаря наличию соответствующих природных объектов. Однако эта сфера туризма пока недостаточно развита. В данной работе сначала дается определение экстремального туризма и описываются его потенциальные преимущества, такие как экономический рост и сохранение природных достопримечательностей. Далее на основе литературы определяются подходящие места для экстремального туризма в Узбекистане. В завершение даются рекомендации по открытию новых туристических агентств, специализирующихся на приключенческих турах, с использованием интернет-платформ для предоставления услуг и продвижения.

Ключевые слова: Узбекистан, экстремальный туризм, интернет-платформа.

Introduction

In the present days, adventure tourism is becoming rapidly progressing type of tourism activities. However, in spite of using a great potential in Uzbekistan, authorities are not paying enough attention to its evolvement. Adventure tourism is the type of tourism which includes the risky activities, such as, bungee and base jumping, hiking, mountaineering, sky diving, canoeing, skiing and many others. These types of sport can be called extreme or even bloody sports because of having a serious danger and threat of death. Precisely, because of this reason extreme tourism attracts young generation and influences to participate in such kind of dangerous experience. “Extreme sports increasingly attract participants from different social classes and age groups, as well as females and minority groups” (Kunwar, 2021). By possessing majestic peaks, endless

deserts and unaltered natural environment, Uzbekistan offers a bunch of opportunities for adrenaline-seeker new generation. As Mirziyoyev mentioned, “The advancement of adventure tourism brings a bunch of privileges for Uzbekistan, such as attraction of new visitors, job creation, economic boost and the protection of natural heritage” (2023). By counting several benefits to both sides, namely, providers and costumers, the new tour organizations should be created which are purposed to promote adventure tourism in Uzbekistan where is “ideal place”. This essay will firstly count appropriate locations for adventure tourism in Uzbekistan, and then will offer to open new specific agencies with the additional convenience which is the service through internet.

Literature review

Uzbekistan is suitable place for extreme tourism. As Mikhliyev and Mallayeva mentioned: “Extreme tourism in Uzbekistan is still in its nascent stages, but it holds immense potential for growth and development” (2023). Initially, extreme sports attract people from different social classes, gender, age. Kunwar conducted a survey that proves “Adventure and risk-taking sports such as mountaineering, whitewater rafting, surfing, skiing, skydiving, downhill mountain biking, rock climbing and base jumping have increased in popularity in recent years” (2021). Furthermore, President of Uzbekistan Mirziyoyev saw the potential of this sphere:

“Extreme tourism is rapidly growing industry that offers a wide range of opportunities for our country. It can help us to attract new visitors, create jobs, and boost our economy. Uzbekistan is a country with a rich history and culture, as well as stunning natural beauty. We have ancient cities, snow-capped mountains, and vast deserts. All of these features make Uzbekistan an ideal destination for extreme tourism enthusiasts” (2023).

From Misirxonov’s (2022) and Alimov’s (2023) surveys, apparently, Uzbekistan has numerous touristic locations which are appropriate for sports, such as, Chimgan, Chatkal, Beldersay, Charvak, Amirsay and others. One convenience that is significant to mention is online reservation of extreme tour packages. As an example, Akaracharyana had observed a website called “advenjourney.com” which simplifies booking a tour. Creation of this kind of websites or platforms will impact to the agencies positively.

Discussions

With the existence of several picturesque and appropriate locations, it is possible to enhance extreme tourism in Uzbekistan. “Uzbekistan is the right place for those who like to do sports in fresh air and away from big cities” (Misirkhonov, 2022). From the questionnaire which was held, most of local residents consider that Uzbekistan has a great chance to improve extreme tourism.

Figure 1

How to improve extreme tourism in Uzbekistan?

How it can be done?
23 responses

Note. Most of the respondents consider that the balance of promotion and quality is crucial factor.

One of the considerable changes will be done soon. It is the resort zone which will be located on 570 hectares along the shore of the Charvak reservoir. The project of Sea Breeze by Emin Agalarov was revealed in social media, which estimated by 10 billion dollars and it is planned to include residential complexes, villas, hotels, restaurants and infrastructure with an emphasis on water sports, a golf course and much more. “Zamin District, situated in the breathtaking Jizzakh region of Uzbekistan, has the significant potential for both domestic and international tourism with its amenities for extreme sport activities” (Abduhakimov, 2021). This district is already well-known for some attractions. One of them is glass-bridge and ropeway which guaranties picturesque view and the activity of bungee jumping was firstly held there in 2023. Apparently, some dangerous sports can be done in water, but unfortunately Uzbekistan is landlocked country. “In spite of lacking access to the huge water sources, there are many places for water tourism - such as the deepwater basin of Charvoq in the foothills of the Western Tien Shan, considerable tidal rivers and huge sea-like Lakes such as Aydarkol, Sudoche and Tashkent Sea” (Misirkhonov, 2021). Still, it is possible to encourage passionate people to try these activities here. “For those who like extreme recreation, many tour operators offer rafting on rivers such as Chotkal, Pskem, Ugam, Syrdaryo and many other places” (Misirkhonov, 2021).

New tour agencies

Uzbekistan does not have adequate specific tour agencies with the purpose of promotion of adventure tourism and this problem should be addressed by government and the involvement of internet should be considered. “The tourism industry in Uzbekistan has long been focused on traditional forms of tourism, such as visiting historical monuments and cultural sites. However, in recent years, there has been a growing interest in extreme tourism, which offers travelers the opportunity to explore Uzbekistan’s stunning natural beauty and unique cultural heritage through activities such as mountain climbing, trekking and paragliding” (Mikhliyev & Mallayeva, 2023). Currently, most of the tour agencies and organizations are focusing on packages of foreign countries with recreational and religious purposes. Therefore, adventure tourism is not getting enough attention for evolvement. By improving conditions of the mentioned locations and providing amenities for dangerous sports, authorities and interested individuals will cover expenditure and earn more. In contrast, tour agency which is called Dagestan tour situated there is doing an amazing job, namely, attracting tourists around the world and promoting business effectively. Marketing and promotion play vital role in enhancement of business which determine the “fate” of organizations. “At present, one of the most internet-used business, such as tour agencies, hotels, airlines and car rentals have become click and mortar organization and use internet to be the important tool for increasing the effectiveness of selling, servicing and advertising” (Akaracharyana, 2003). Furthermore, offering platform of reservation online will bring privileges for customers making it easy to book tour packages without going somewhere, as well as, depicts choices- locations with activities. This operation brings benefits for both sides: “minimizes cost of operation, minimizes time on servicing and contacting, competitive advantage, makes able to control information to the customers, makes customers have more convenience in planning their trip, reservation online can service customers 24 hours a day and 7 days a week” (Akaracharyana, 2003). Additionally, advertising through social media likely to engage more people in contrast with traditional forms of advertisement.

Figure 2

The impact of the Internet to promotion

What do you think, can Internet have an impact on promotion of those locations and activities? (Extreme sports)
23 responses

Note. Most of the respondents estimated the influence of internet highly.

Thus, with the costumers’ reviews reputation of the agencies and faith of future clients will increase.

Conclusion

In conclusion, although adventure tourism in Uzbekistan is still considered as a minor sector of tourism industry, by right promotion it can bring several advantages. Nevertheless, current generation, specifically, young voyagers are more likely to search for active and challenging experiences. The advancement of adventure tourism in Uzbekistan has the possibility to bring several privileges to country’s economy, including a huge profit from tourism industry, and the protection of both natural and cultural side of it. To achieve this goal, it is important to establish specialized tour agencies focused on extreme tourism, invest in infrastructure at natural sites, and launch integrated online platforms that are accessible to information and simplify booking process. Additionally, improvement of marketing strategies and organization of extreme sport events could boost the number of visitors. “Uzbekistan offers numerous opportunities for extreme sports due to its vast and diverse landscapes, although these sports are still new in the country” (Alimov, 2023). By implementing mentioned measures, Uzbekistan will be capable to use its natural landscapes effectively to strengthen its tourism industry, protect its cultural and natural heritage, and impact to the economic growth.

REFERENCES

1. Abduhakimov, Sh. S. (2023). Improvement of internal and external tourism potential of Zamin district of Jizzakh region. *Social sciences and humanities research fundamentals*, 03(07), 33-36. <https://doi.org/10.55640/jsshrf-03-07-09>
2. Akaracharyana, M. (2003). Online reservation for adventure tour packages www.advenjourney.com. A final report of the Three-Credit Course IC 6997 E-Commerce practicum.
3. Alimov, A. (2023). Development of tourism business in mountainous areas. *Sustainable economic development of regions: international and national concepts*, 110-119.

4. Kunwar, R. R. (2021). Extreme sport: understanding the concept, recognizing the value. *Tourism & adventure*, 4(1), 89-123.
5. Mikhliyev, M. Mallayeva, S. (2023). The prospects for the development of extreme tourism in Uzbekistan. *Multidisciplinary research*, 1(8), 67-75.
6. Misirkhonov, Kh. I. (2022). Sports in the development of tourism. *Fan, ta'lim, madaniyat va innovatsiya*, 01(5), 32-34.